

Angelo Leogrande^{1*o}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Early Exit from the Education and Training System in the Italian Regions

It decreased by 20.25% between 2018 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of leaving the education and training system early. The variable is defined as the percentage of people aged 18-24 with at most a lower secondary school diploma-middle school diploma, who do not possess professional qualifications obtained in courses lasting at least 2 years and not included in an education or training course for the total number of people aged 18-24. The data refers to the period 2018-2022.

Ranking of Italian regions by value of early exit from the education and training system. Sicily is in first place for the value of early exit from the education and training system with a value of 18.8 units, followed by Campania with an amount of 16.1 and Sardinia with a value of 14.7. In the middle of the table are Liguria and Calabria with an amount of 10.3 units, followed by Lombardy with an amount of 9.9 units. Umbria closes the ranking with a value of 7.3 units, followed by Marche with an amount of 5.8 units and Basilicata with a value of 5.3 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change between 2018 and 2022 in the value of early exit from the education and training system. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of the percentage change between 2018 and 2022 of early exit from the education and training system with a value of 17.98% or equal to an amount of 1.6 units, followed by 'Abruzzo with an amount of 10.71% equal to an amount of 0.9 units, followed by Tuscany with an amount of 3.88% equal to an amount of 0.4 units. In the middle of the table are Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount of -13.48% equal to an amount of -1.2 units, followed by Sicily with an amount of -14.55%, Puglia with an amount of -17.05%. The Marche closes the ranking with an amount of -40.21% equal to an amount of -3.9 units, followed by Calabria with a value of -48.5% equal to an amount of -9.76 units, and Basilicata with a value of -51.82% equal to an amount of -5.7 units. Overall between 2018 and 2022 the value of early exit from the education and training system -20.25%.

Italian macro-regions. The value of early exit from the education and training system in Northern Italy decreased from an amount of 12.00 units to a value of 9.90 units or a reduction equal to an amount of -2.10 units, equal to a value of -17.50%. The value of early exit from the education and training system decreased in the North-West from an amount of 13.20 units to a value of 10.20 units or equal to a reduction of -3.00 units equivalent to a value of -22.73%. The value of early exit from the education and training system in the North-East decreased from an amount of 10.50 units to a value of 9.40 units or equal to a variation of -1.10 units apparently a value of -10.48%. The value of early exit from the training and education system went from an amount of 10.40 units to a value of 8.20 units or equal to a variation of -2.20 units equal to a value of -21.25%. The value of early exit from the training and education system in Southern Italy went from an amount of 18.70 units in 2018

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

to a value of 15.10 units in 2022 or a reduction equal to an amount of -3, 60 units equal to a value of -19.25%. The value of early exit from the training and education system in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 17.10 units to a value of 13.80 units or equal to a reduction of -3.30 units equal to a value of -19.30%. The value of early exit from the training and education system in the Islands decreased from an amount of 22.20 units in 2018 to a value of 17.90 units in 2022 or equal to a value of -4.30 units equal to an amount of -19.37%. The value of early exit from the training and education system in Italy decreased from an amount of 14.30 units to a value of 11.50 units or equal to a reduction of -2.80 units equal to a value by -19.58%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

- *Cluster 1:* Emilia Romagna, Veneto, Trentino-Alto Adige, Abruzzo, Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Tuscany, Molise, Umbria, Basilicata, Piedmont, Liguria, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta;
- *Cluster 2:* Campania, Puglia, Calabria, Sicily, Sardinia.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters, it appears that the value of Cluster 2 is higher than the value of Cluster 1, i.e.: $C2 > C1$. It follows that the value of early exit from the training and education system tends to be higher in the southern regions than in the central-northern regions, with the exception of Abruzzo, Molise and Basilicata. However, considering the period between 2018 and 2022, it appears that the value of school dropouts in the cluster 2 regions tends to be decreasing. It follows that there will most likely be a convergence in the value of early exit from the education and training system in the southern regions compared to the corresponding value in the Central-Northern regions or the Cluster 1 regions.

Conclusions. The value of early exit from the education and training system decreased between 2018 and 2022 by an amount equal to a value of 20.25. The results therefore show significant progress in almost all Italian regions. However, as almost always in regional metrics, a gap persists between the southern regions and the regions of Central-Northern Italy. It is therefore necessary to invest further in training to increase convergence between the southern regions and the central-northern regions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University "Giuseppe Degennaro" and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6516438>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Individuals with Risk Behaviors in the Consumption of Alcohol in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636364>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* [https://ilsudest.it/. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551](https://ilsudest.it/.https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551)
- Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Years of Life Lost for Exposure to PM2.5 in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799937>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2023). The Perception of Good Health in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799948>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Healthy Life Expectancy in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799956>
- Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Nitrate in Groundwater in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799995>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Ammonia Emissions in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806877>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Use of Hazardous Pesticides in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806908>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Areas Cultivated with Organic Agriculture in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806941>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Public Expenditure for Research and Development in Agriculture in EU, USA, and Japan. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806965>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). The Material and Social Deprivation in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811428>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Workers at Risk of Poverty in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811442>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). Turnover in the Service Sector in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811492>

Angelo Leogrando. (2023). People Who Remain Poor Even After Social Transfers in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811683>

Appendix

Uscita Precoce dal Sistema dell'Istruzione e della Formazione tra il 2018 ed il 2022							
Regione	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	★ 13,5	★ 10,7	★ 12,1	★ 11,4	★ 11	★ -2,50	★ -18,52
Valle d'Aosta	★ 15,1	★ 14,1	★ 13,2	★ 14,1	★ 13,3	★ -1,80	★ -11,92
Liguria	★ 12,8	★ 9,7	★ 10	★ 12,9	★ 10,3	★ -2,50	★ -19,53
Lombardia	★ 13,1	★ 11,3	★ 13,1	★ 11,3	★ 9,9	★ -3,20	★ -24,43
Trentino-Alto Adige	★ 8,9	★ 9,2	★ 10,8	★ 10,9	★ 10,5	★ 1,60	★ 17,98
Veneto	★ 10,9	★ 8,3	★ 11,2	★ 9,3	★ 9,5	★ -1,40	★ -12,84
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 8,9	★ 8,7	★ 8,8	★ 8,6	★ 7,7	★ -1,20	★ -13,48
Emilia-Romagna	★ 10,8	★ 11,1	★ 10,1	★ 9,9	★ 9,5	★ -1,30	★ -12,04
Toscana	★ 10,3	★ 10,1	★ 12,9	★ 11,1	★ 10,7	★ 0,40	★ 3,88
Umbria	★ 8,3	★ 9,3	★ 12,6	★ 12	★ 7,3	★ -1,00	★ -12,05
Marche	★ 9,7	★ 8,5	★ 9,2	★ 7,9	★ 5,8	★ -3,90	★ -40,21
Lazio	★ 11	★ 11,6	★ 12,2	★ 9,2	★ 7,4	★ -3,60	★ -32,73
Abruzzo	★ 8,4	★ 9,9	★ 10,1	★ 8	★ 9,3	★ 0,90	★ 10,71
Molise	★ 10,2	★ 10,7	★ 9,2	★ 7,6	★ 8,3	★ -1,90	★ -18,63
Campania	★ 18,4	★ 17,2	★ 19	★ 16,4	★ 16,1	★ -2,30	★ -12,50
Puglia	★ 17,6	★ 17,8	★ 18,5	★ 17,6	★ 14,6	★ -3,00	★ -17,05
Basilicata	★ 11	★ 11,7	★ 13,6	★ 8,7	★ 5,3	★ -5,70	★ -51,82
Calabria	★ 20	★ 18,9	★ 16,9	★ 14	★ 10,3	★ -9,70	★ -48,50
Sicilia	★ 22	★ 22,3	★ 21,8	★ 21,2	★ 18,8	★ -3,20	★ -14,55
Sardegna	★ 22,8	★ 17,7	★ 12,9	★ 13,2	★ 14,7	★ -8,10	★ -35,53

Macro-Regioni	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022-2018
<i>Nord</i>	★ 12,00	★ 10,30	★ 11,70	★ 10,70	★ 9,90	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -1,70	★ 1,40	★ -1,00	★ -0,80	★ -2,10
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -14,17	★ 13,59	★ -8,55	★ -7,48	★ -17,50
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	★ 13,20	★ 11,00	★ 12,60	★ 11,50	★ 10,20	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -2,20	★ 1,60	★ -1,10	★ -1,30	★ -3,00
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -16,67	★ 14,55	★ -8,73	★ -11,30	★ -22,73
<i>Nord-est</i>	★ 10,50	★ 9,50	★ 10,50	★ 9,60	★ 9,40	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -1,00	★ 1,00	★ -0,90	★ -0,20	★ -1,10
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -9,52	★ 10,53	★ -8,57	★ -2,08	★ -10,48
<i>Centro</i>	★ 10,40	★ 10,60	★ 12,00	★ 9,80	★ 8,20	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ 0,20	★ 1,40	★ -2,20	★ -1,60	★ -2,20
<i>Var Per</i>		★ 1,92	★ 13,21	★ -18,33	★ -16,33	★ -21,15
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	★ 18,70	★ 18,10	★ 18,20	★ 16,60	★ 15,10	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -0,60	★ 0,10	★ -1,60	★ -1,50	★ -3,60
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -3,21	★ 0,55	★ -8,79	★ -9,04	★ -19,25
<i>Sud</i>	★ 17,10	★ 16,70	★ 17,50	★ 15,30	★ 13,80	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -0,40	★ 0,80	★ -2,20	★ -1,50	★ -3,30
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -2,34	★ 4,79	★ -12,57	★ -9,80	★ -19,30
<i>Isole</i>	★ 22,20	★ 21,30	★ 19,90	★ 19,50	★ 17,90	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -0,90	★ -1,40	★ -0,40	★ -1,60	★ -4,30
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -4,05	★ -6,57	★ -2,01	★ -8,21	★ -19,37
<i>Italia</i>	★ 14,30	★ 13,30	★ 14,20	★ 12,70	★ 11,50	
<i>Var Ass</i>		★ -1,00	★ 0,90	★ -1,50	★ -1,20	★ -2,80
<i>Var Per</i>		★ -6,99	★ 6,77	★ -10,56	★ -9,45	★ -19,58

